

THE ROLE OF SCIENCE EDUCATION IN MEETING THE CHALLENGES OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

Onyia Comfort Ngozi

Department of Chemistry, School of Science Education, Enugu State College of Education (Technical), Enugu.

Iketaku Ifeoma Roseline

Department of Educational Psychology, School of Science Education
Enugu State College of Education (Technical), Enugu.

KEYWORDS: learning, science and technology, development strategies, economic growth, social wellbeing

ABSTRACT

There is increasing realization that learning and applying science and technology to development strategies could produce major improvements in economic growth and social wellbeing in Nigeria. This paper considered the aims and objectives of science education with emphasis on education not schooling. In addition the constraints to the realization of the goals (such as poor achievement in science and lack of interest, poor teaching methods, inadequate funding, lack of science teachers) were considered. The input of Science Education towards our economy, food, medical and communication was also x-rayed. The paper recommended that enough funding, provision of competent teachers and availability of committed stakeholders in science education should be in place for it to sincerely and genuinely serve as a vehicle for national development in Nigeria among others.

INTRODUCTION

The important of science education in the development of a nation cannot be over emphasized. It is the foundation of practical changes and development of any society. There has been an increased attention in science education and learning in developing countries of the world in order to produce more and better trained scientist and technologists, in order to thrive technologically in today's world – global village. According is Iwuala (1990), a close look at human history will show that science and technology, whether in pre-historic rudimentary forms, or in the modern day sophisticated and complex forms, have continued to keep pace with the challenges and ever- growing complexities of man.

Science according to Aniodo (2002), in Egbo and Aniodo (2010) is an organized knowledge that has been gathered through many years of careful observations, experiments and reasoning. It also means the systematic study of the empirical world in order to understand it.

One of the aims and objectives of tertiary education as outlined in the education policy document (FME; 2004) is to produce manpower in science, technology and mathematics so as to increase agricultural and economics development in Nigerians". In order to achieve this objectives, manpower development in higher institutions of learning should be well focused and directed towards the achievement of these aims:-

- i) To contribute to the national development by intensifying and diversifying their prograammes for the development of high level manpower according to the needs of the economy with emphasis on science, technology and mathematics
- ii) To produce manpower capable of applying the acquired knowledge in improving and solving their environmental problems thus making it more useful and convenient for man.
- iii) To produce manpower capable of effectively utilizing scientific knowledge and methods in solving real life problems such as food, shelter, health, water resources, energy etc.

In transforming there aims and objectives into reality, such curricula were redesigned to reflect science, technology and mathematics at all levels of nations school system.

Goals of Science Education

These objectives of tertiary education can be fully achieved through emphasizing the goals of science of education stated in the National Policy on Education, thus;

- i. to cultivates inquiry, knowledge and rational mind for the conduct of a good life and democracy
- ii. to produce scientist for national development
- iii. services studies is technology and the cause of technological development and
- v. to provide knowledge and understanding of the complexity of the physical world, the forms and the conduct of life (FRN, 2004).

It simply means that science and technology education, if properly taught, will instill in the future scientist the scientific attitudes of honestly, suspended judgment, humility, curiosity, objectively to mention but a few. They will also develop in them the scientific process skills of observation, experimentation, manipulative skills, formulating hypothecs and models which consist the vehicles or process through which the **learner scientist** becomes scientifically and technologically literate, self employed and self sufficient (Maduabum 1989). Imperatively self sufficiency will raise living standard of the citizenry. With the learner scientist being scientifically and technologically self employed, they can contribute their quota to the national development. The nation will also be scientifically and technologically developed hence meeting the challenges of tertiary institution of tertiary institutions towards national development.

Teachers' Role in Meeting the Challenges.

Teachers (Lecturers) need to make science effective and relevant to a diverse fraction of population and nation at large. To do this, the following facts need to be critically enforced on the students in order for science teaching and learning to make any meaningful impact in the national development. These are; Research in learning, retaining information, understanding basic concepts, affecting beliefs and improving teaching and learning.

Research in Learning

In a traditional science class, the teacher stands at front of the class lecturing to a largely passive group of students. These students then go off and do back-of-the chapter home-work problems from the textbook and take exams that are similar to these exercise and pass without any knowledge of research. It has been noted by Hasteners and Swackhammer (1992) that new graduate "scientist" after years of extraordinary success in class, when given research projects to work on were clueless about how to proceed. Or worse – often it seemed that they did not even really understand the concept at all.

Teachers should therefore teach and make sure that any graduate of science should be drilled practically to be able to undertake research works in order to contribute to the nations cry for technological advancement.

Retaining Information

Teachers should not be surprised to find out that students are able to take away only a small fraction of what is presented to them from lectures. They take in information and retain such longer when they are involved and see those things done. (Hake 1998) therefore teachers should ensure that science is taught with practical and demonstration lessons.

Understanding Basic Concept

There are fundamental concepts in science that can be applied very widely. This has inspired science education researchers to study how well students are actually learning the basic concepts in their science courses. The oldest and the most widely used assessment tool in Physics for example is the Force Concepts Inventory (FCI) Hestenes (1992). This tests student's mastery of the basic concept and their application to real – world context. Hake (1998) found out that students who mastered many basic concepts are assets and catalysts to the technological development of a nation. Teachers should ensure pedagogical approaches involving more interactive engagement of students to help them master the basic concepts.

Affecting Belief

Students believe certain things about what science is and how one goes about learning the discipline. Beliefs about science lies on a spectrum that ranges from “novice” to “expert” Hake (1999). It is the implicit belief that science is difficult. Traditional science instruction concentrates on teaching factual knowledge with the implicit assumption that expert – like ways of thinking about the subject comes along naturally or are already present. The teacher therefore has to involve cognitive science which holds that students need to develop expert ways of thinking by means of extended, focused mental **effort**. Basic biology tells us that everything that constitutes understanding “science and other thinking scientifically” resides in the long – term memory, which is developed via the construction and assembly of component protein. A person who does not go through this extended mental construction cannot achieve mastery of a subject.

Improving Teaching and Learning

Scientific knowledge is dynamic and ever changing. It is often said that the only thing that is permanent in nature is change itself (Anidoh 2008).

The traditional lecture method of teaching science should as a matter of fact be replaced with experimentation, demonstration and inquiry base methods which give the students opportunity to see, do, and interact with one another and with the environment. Secondly incorporation of desirable cognitive activities into normal course activities should be one of the keys for them to be relevant and make meaning contribution to the technologically changing world.

Challenges of Tertiary Institutions in Meeting the Demands of the Nation Technologically.

The institution in the nation are facing a number of challenges towards meeting the demand of Nation’s scientific technological demands such problems are as follows:

Inadequate Funding of Education:

The information published by Academic Staff Union of the Universities (ASUU) on government funding on education and cited in Nwabuisi (2008) in Eze and Oluba (2010) is as follows; in 1999, the budgetary allocation was 11.12%, in 2000, it was 8.36%; in 2001, 7.0%; in 2002, it was 5.9% and in 2003, it was 1.83%. There is a big decrease in the amount budgeted for education and this goes a long way to account for inadequacy of funds to equip our institutions for maximum technological harnessing. Most of our laboratories are shadows of the real thing. Teachers/Lecturers do not enjoy financial rewards from the Government commensurate with their contributions to development (Madukwe 2001) hence the current ASUU strike nationwide.

Lack of Laboratory Facilities:

One of the roles of science education towards national development is to sustain the growth, and also improve the efficiency of the national economy. If our laboratories are not adequately equipped with modern facilities, there will not be any meaningful research work done and thus we will continue to be dependent on other thus affecting our economy negatively.

Shortage of Well – Qualified and Enthusiastic Science Teacher

Madukwe (2001), in Oluba and Eze (2010) opined that any country that is desirous development whether scientifically, technologically or general should pay utmost attention to its teachers.

One of the goals of science education according to Ugwu and Ozioko (2010) is to promote improvisation, innovative thinking, creativity and resourcefulness and use of knowledge and skills acquired to provide national needs and solve personal and societal problems. This will remain an illusion if there are no well qualified and enthusiastic sciences teachers for the transfer of such knowledge.

Lack of Meaningful Research

One of the major problems of undertaking meaningful research is lack of fund to equip the laboratories where the desired meaningful research can be carried out. With the shabby state of most laboratories in our institutions of higher learning, most works that should involve research are done theoretically.

Over Emphasis on Cognitive Development

There is over-emphasis on the acquisition of certificate rather than in actual acquisition of knowledge and skills. This has resulted in the pursuit of certificate at all cost through any means available. This has resulted in the student's interest in passing the exam without paying attention to the actual knowledge involved which can be transferred to national development. The opinion of Maduabum (2001) in Eze and Oluba (2010) is a contrary one which says that **“ours is a country with no education system but certification system”**. In which University science graduates are turned out from institutions which are better described as simple, glorified secondary schools having learnt about science not science its self”.

CONCLUSION

Science education plays very important roles in triggering off technological advancement and hence national development, a nation without strong science education base remains a consumer nation and underdeveloped. In view of this, the institutions of higher learning as channels through which this is achieved should be given a face lift in terms of funding, research, to mention but a few, for the nation to be technologically and scientifically viable.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the challenges identified, the paper therefore recommends thus;

1. There is urgent need for the government to give priority attention to education during budgeting such that enough funds will be injected to the education sector, science and science education in particular.
2. Stakeholders in the education sector in Nigeria should pay serious attention to the development of science education by ensuring that enough fund is allotted to schools for equipping the laboratories and that such funds are judiciously used. They should also ensure implementation of science and technology programmes.
3. Government and infact the governing councils of various institutions of higher learning should ensure that they employ only well qualified and enthusiastic science teachers who will inculcate into the students scientific values and consciousness.
4. Government should join force with stakeholders to make sure that everything needed by these institutions to establish a research base should be put in place in all institutions of higher learning in the nation.
5. Laws should be enacted by the government that in addition to paper qualification a practical session/written work should be the basis for employment in both private and public sectors of the work force of the nation.

REFERENCES

- Aniodo H.C.O. (1990) *“Application of science and Technology to Life Situations. The Nigerian Experience”*. Imo State STAN Conference Owerri.
- Aniodo H.C.O. (2001). *Science, Technology and Society*. Enugu, Hacofam Educational Books.
- Aniodo H.C.O. (2002). *History and Philosophy of Science, Enugu, Hacofam Educational Books*.
- Aniodo H.C.O. and Egbo Joy John Best (2010). *Promoting Democracy Through Science Education*, Enugu. NAPFED.

VENUE: FRANCIS IDIBIYE HALL, FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, AKURE, ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

8TH – 9TH, OCTOBER, 2013

Eze C.U. and Oluba B.C. *Refocusing Sciences Education in Nigeria for National Development*. Enugu. John Best Enterprises Ltd.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (1992). *National Philosophy of Teacher Education in Nigeria Kaduna: NCCE*.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004): *National Policy on Education*. Lagos. NERDC Press.

Hake R. (1998). *The American Journal of Physics*.

Hesteners, M. (1992). *Science Education Initiative*. Colorado.

Hesteners, M. Walls, G. Swackhammer (1992). *The Physics Teachers*.

Iwuala, M.O. (1990). “*Applications of Science and Technology to life situations. The Nigerian Experience*”. Imo State STAN Conference Owerri.

Maduabum, M.A. (1989). *Teaching Integrated Science Effectively*. Onitsha Space Martrix Publications Ltd.

Maduabum, M.A. (2001). Intervention Packages STM, in Mogbo J.O. (Ed). *National Policy on Education for Sustainable Developmental Issues for 21st Century*. Enugu. Faculty of Education ESUT.

Nwabuisi E.M. (2008). *Education for What?* Nsukka; UNN Press Ltd.

Ugwu and Ozioko (2010). Science Education and Global Economic Meltdown. *Nigerian Journal of Functional Education*, Enugu. Published by National Association for the Promotion of Functional Education (NAPFED).